

Studies on 5-(Indan-1'-yl)tetrazoles as Potential Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Agents

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Manuscript received 15 March 1989, revised 22 November 1989, accepted 6 December 1989

A few 5-(indan-1'-yl)tetrazoles and their intermediates were synthesised and screened for anti-inflammatory and related biological activities. 5-(Indan-1'-yl)tetrazole was found to be superior to phenylbutazone in 'established' adjuvant-induced arthritis and yeast-induced pyrexia biomodels in rats.

5-SUBSTITUTED tetrazoles are metabolically stable acidic functions having comparable acidity as that of corresponding carboxylic acids^{1,2}. Several workers have reported retention^{3,4} or improvement⁵ or even abolition⁶ of biological activity of various carboxylic acids on replacement of carboxyl function by 5-tetrazolyl group. Encouraging results with the 5-(indan-1'-yl)methyltetrazoles have already been reported from this laboratory^{7,8}. We, therefore, undertook synthesis and screening of a few more tetrazole analogues of already reported⁹ anti-inflammatory indan-1-carboxylic acids (**1**) with a view to get better anti-inflammatory agents. The present communication deals with the synthesis of the title compounds (**4**) from the corresponding indan-1-carboxylic acids (**1**) via the intermediate amides (**2**) and nitriles (**3**) (Scheme 1). These tetrazoles (**4**) and their intermediate amides (**2**) were subjected to both acute and chronic anti-inflammatory screening and **4** were also put to analgesic and antipyretic screening tests. In view of relatively poor performance of indan-1-acetonitriles¹⁰, the corresponding indan-1-carbonitriles (**2**) were not subjected to biological screening.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries in liquid paraffin bath and are uncorrected.

Identity and purity of the compounds were ascertained by elemental microanalysis and spectral analysis. Uv, ir (thin film or nujol) and nmr spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 200-20 uv-vis spectrophotometer, a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 297 spectrophotometer and a Jeol JNM-FX-100 FT-NMR spectrometer respectively. Spectral data of the compounds gave characteristic bands¹¹⁻¹³ of their respective functional groups. Elemental microanalysis of all the compounds conformed well with their proposed structures.

The key intermediates, indan-1-carboxylic acids (**1**) were synthesised by the general method of cyclodehydration of the phenylsuccinic acids with polyphosphoric acid and subsequent reduction of the resulting indan-3-one-1-carboxylic acids as reported earlier¹⁴. Only phenylsuccinic acid was cyclised with anhydrous AlCl₃¹⁵. However, it was found that substituted phenylsuccinic acids could be prepared in more than 60% of the theoretical yield starting from 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde or vanillin over four steps following the method of Ogawa and Matsui¹⁶, whereas the route formerly adopted¹⁴ gave an overall yield of 32% only over four steps starting from the same aldehydes.

Indan-1-carboxamides (2): The compounds were synthesised from the corresponding indan-1-carboxylic acids (**1**) via the acyl halide intermediates by reaction with dry NH₃ following standard procedures.

Indan-1-carboxamide (2a): **1a** (16.2 g, 0.1 mol) yielded **2a** (14.7 g, 91%), m.p. 158–60° from aqueous MeOH (Found: C, 74.63; H, 7.19; N, 8.52. C₁₀H₁₁ON requires: C, 74.51; H, 6.88; N, 8.69%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 355, 3 170 (NH) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=O); **6-Methoxyindan-1-carboxamide (2b)**; 88–90%, m.p. 166–67° from MeOH (Found: C, 68.95; H, 7.22; N, 7.19. C₁₁H₁₃O₂N requires: C, 69.09; H, 6.85; N, 7.32%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 315, 3 145 (NH), 1 665 (C=O) and 1 190 cm⁻¹ (OCH₃); **5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-carboxamide (2c)**; 88–94%, m.p. 169–71° from aqueous MeOH (Found: C, 65.22; H, 7.12; N, 6.13. C₁₂H₁₅O₃N requires:

C, 65.14; H, 6.83; N, 6.33%; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 305, 3 220 (NH), 1 660 (C=O) and 1 190 cm^{-1} (OCH₃).

Indan-1-carbonitrile (3a): It was prepared from **2a** (16.1 g, 0.1 mol) on dehydration with POCl₃ (0.6 mol) and Na₂S₂O₅ (0.06 mol) following the method of Mihina and Herbst¹⁷ (81%, 11.6 g), b.p. 115–18°/0.5 mm Hg (Found: C, 83.97; H, 6.04; N, 9.96 C₁₀H₉N requires: C, 83.88; H, 6.34; N, 9.78%); η_D^{20} 1.5406; ν_{\max} (thin film) 2 230 cm^{-1} (C≡N).

6-Methoxyindan-1-carbonitrile (3b): The method adopted for **3a** was followed to obtain **3b** from **2b** (83–84%), b.p. 132–33°/0.7 mm Hg (Found: C, 76.19; H, 6.57; N, 7.96. C₁₁H₁₁ON requires: C, 76.28; H, 6.40; N, 8.09%); η_D^{20} 1.5446; ν_{\max} (thin film) 2 230 (C≡N) and 1 195 cm^{-1} (OCH₃).

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-carbonitrile (3c): The method of Mihina and Herbst¹⁷, modified by omission of Na₂S₂O₅, was employed for synthesis of **3c** from **2c**. The solid thus obtained was crystallised from a large volume of H₂O to yield **3c** (78–79%), m.p. 101–02° (Found: C, 70.76; H, 6.31; N, 7.23. C₁₂H₁₃O₂N requires: C, 70.92; H, 6.45; N, 6.89%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 2 220 (C≡N) and 1 195 cm^{-1} (OCH₃).

5-(Indan-1'-yl)tetrazole (4a): It was prepared by refluxing a mixture of **3a** (6.5 g, 0.045 mol), activated NaN₃ (5.91 g, 0.09 mol), dry NH₄Cl (4.86 g, 0.09 mol) in dry DMF (40 ml) at 120–30° for 18 h following the method of Finnegan *et al.*¹⁸. DMF was then distilled off under reduced pressure from a steam-bath. The solid mass was taken up in warm 5% aqueous KOH solution. The cooled alkaline solution, after filtration and subsequent Et₂O extraction, was made acidic with concentrated HCl to ~pH 2 under cooling. The resulting solid was treated with decolourising carbon and recrystallised from H₂O to give **4a** (4.35 g) in 55% yield. m.p. 146–47° (Found: C, 64.17; H, 5.68; N, 30.14. C₁₀H₁₀N₄ requires: C, 64.50; H, 5.41; N, 30.09%); λ_{\max} (H₂O) 265 and 271.6 nm (ϵ_{\max} 927 and 882 respectively); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 570 (C=N cyclic), 1 275 (N=N–N), 1 108 and 1 045 cm^{-1} (tetrazole ring vibration); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 2.52 (2H, m, 2'-CH₂), 3.06 (2H, quin, 3'-CH₂), 4.78 (1H, t, 1'-CH) and 7.18 (4H, qm, ArH).

5-(6'-Methoxyindan-1'-yl)tetrazole (4b): It was synthesised following the method of Finnegan *et al.*¹⁸ (refluxing for 24 h) from **3b** (54%), m.p. 179–81° (from EtOAc) (Found: C, 60.98; H, 5.76; N, 25.73. C₁₁H₁₂ON₄ requires: C, 61.10; H, 5.59; N, 25.91%); λ_{\max} (H₂O) 280 nm (ϵ_{\max} 3 007); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 580 (C=N cyclic), 1 275 (N=N–N), 1 180 (OCH₃), 1 097 and 1 025 cm^{-1} (tetrazole ring vibration); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 2.50 (2H, m, 2'-CH₂), 2.95 (2H, quin, 3'-CH₂), 3.68 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.75 (1H, t, 1'-CH), 6.68 (1H, s, 7'-ArH), 6.82 (1H, d, 5'-ArH) and 7.20 (1H, d, 4'-ArH).

5-(5',6'-Dimethoxyindan-1'-yl)tetrazole (4c): It was synthesised in the same way as **4a** (refluxing for

36 h) from **3c** (44%), m.p. 162–64° (from H₂O) (Found: C, 58.93; H, 5.86; N, 22.46. C₁₂H₁₄O₂N₄ requires: C, 58.53; H, 5.73; N, 22.75%); λ_{\max} (H₂O) 285.4 nm (ϵ_{\max} 5 163); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 560 (C=N cyclic), 1 280 (N=N–N), 1 190 (OCH₃), 1 085 and 1 048 cm^{-1} (tetrazole ring vibration); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 2.50 (2H, m, 2'-CH₂), 2.90 (2H, quin, 3'-CH₂), 3.66 (3H, s, 6'-OCH₃), 3.74 (3H, s, 5'-OCH₃), 4.65 (1H, t, 1'-CH), 6.74 (1H, s, 7'-ArH) and 6.91 (1H, s, 4'-ArH).

Pharmacology: The compounds (100 mg/kg, P.O.) were screened for acute anti-inflammatory activity in the carrageenan-induced rat hind paw oedema model following the method of Winter *et al.*¹⁹ with minor modifications²⁰, and for chronic anti-inflammatory activity in the 'established' adjuvant-induced arthritis model in rats according to the method of Newbould²¹. Joint-mobility was also assessed²². Antipyretic activity was screened in yeast-induced pyrexia model in rats²³ and 'temperature-index' was calculated according to Winter and Nuss²⁴. For analgesic efficacy testing, phenyl-*p*-quinone-induced mouse writhing test²⁵ was employed. Phenylbutazone was used as the reference standard in all of the screening tests.

Results and Discussion

It was found that bathochromic effect of methoxy substitutions in **4b** and **4c** resulted in red-shift of λ_{\max} , subsequent merger of the peaks (cf. **4a**) and consequent increase in ϵ_{\max} .

The 1-H (NH) proton of the tetrazole derivatives could not be detected in nmr spectra, possibly because of high tautomeric exchange between 1 and 2 positions at the temperature of scanning (50°) required for solubility. Deuteration of the samples did not cause and of the peaks to disappear.

Compounds **2a–c** and **4a–c** exhibited variable anti-inflammatory activity at 3 h after carrageenan administration (% inhibition: **2a**, 18.64; **2b**, 15.86; **2c**, 13.71; **4a**, 28.03; **4b**, 6.79; **4c**, 12.84) compared to phenylbutazone (47.30%) in acute screening. However, they retained significant residual activity even at 24 h (% inhibition: **2a**, 14.39; **2b**, 24.68; **2c**, 19.79; **4a**, 31.31; **4b**, 14.34; **4c**, 18.04 and phenylbutazone, 19.25) which necessitated their further screening in chronic anti-inflammatory models – and **4a** turned out to be superior to phenylbutazone in adjuvant-induced arthritis biomodel. Tetrazoles, in general, showed better antipyretic activity in rats and was found to be slightly less potent in phenyl-*p*-quinone-induced mouse writhing test at the dose level employed. Detailed pharmacological evaluation results will be communicated elsewhere.

The findings necessitate further physicochemical, pharmacological and toxicological evaluation of these agents. Studies on these lines are in progress and are to be reported elsewhere.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank M/s Alembic Chemical Works Co. Ltd. (India), for a gift of phenylbutazone B.P. One of the authors (S.M.R.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for a fellowship.

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